

Hydrogen production using gallium and aluminium waste with spent coffee grounds and tea leaves in seawater

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ABSTRACT

Growing global energy demand and the needs for net-zero alternatives require efficient hydrogen (H₂) production. Using the aluminium–water reaction with aluminium from waste sources, this project aims to determine the optimal aluminium–gallium (Al–Ga) ratio to maximise H₂ yield and gallium recovery and to investigate the effects of spent coffee grounds, spent tea leaves, and fruits in seawater on H₂ yield. Experiments were conducted on Al–Ga ratios, temperature, chelators, sodium chloride (NaCl) concentrations, and different aluminium types. H₂ volume, reaction rate and gallium recovery were measured. Higher temperature and chelator concentration increased hydrogen but may impact gallium recovery. An optimal gallium content of 80 wt% achieved 88.33% H₂ yield and 90.30% gallium recovery with 0.05 M NaCl and 1% spent coffee grounds, while 1% spent tea leaves with 0.05M NaCl achieved 85.12% hydrogen yield and 97.40% gallium recovery. Lemon proved to be the most effective chelator, achieving an H₂ yield of 93.15% and 97.30% gallium recovery in seawater. Total gallium recovery was further increased to 99.91% with centrifugation. These results demonstrate a low-cost pathway for on-site H₂ generation using food and aluminium waste, provide quantitative benchmarks for gallium recovery in saline media, and offer a foundation for scaling waste-to-hydrogen processes in coastal, remote, and circular-economy energy systems.

KEYWORDS: Aluminium-Gallium, Seawater Catalysis, Food Waste Upcycling, Hydrogen Production

1. INTRODUCTION

As we enter the Fourth Industrial Revolution, technologies such as artificial intelligence, quantum computing, and robotics automation are exponentially increasing global energy demand. Total primary energy demand is projected to rise from 644 to 760 EJ by 2050.¹ Nevertheless, 80.4% of our energy consumption still relies on non-renewables, and important ones like oil and natural gas will run out by 2074 and 2069, respectively.² Combusting fossil fuels releases harmful pollutants, causing severe environmental and health damage. Fossil fuel carbon emissions have grown to 36.8 billion tonnes, comprising 89% of all greenhouse gas emissions.³ Thus, identifying low-emission energy sources and reducing dependence on non-renewables will accommodate growing populations while mitigating climate change.

Hydrogen (H₂) stands out as a promising clean energy carrier, with approximately three times the energy density as diesel or liquefied natural gas. Its ability to decarbonise hard-to-electrify industries, such as steelmaking, heavy transport, and aviation, positions hydrogen as a key enabler of a net-zero future.⁴ Emitting no carbon at the point of use, it is an environmentally friendly alternative to fossil fuels. In the coming years, as nations aim towards decarbonising and diversifying energy sources, the demand for H₂ could grow to a \$1.66 trillion market by 2050.⁵ While green H₂ is produced from renewable sources such as solar, wind, or biomass, it accounts for only 0.04% of global production due to high production costs of \$12 per kilogram.⁶ In contrast, Grey H₂ accounts for around 95% of global production and is generated from fossil fuels. It emits 24 kg of CO₂ per kilogram of H₂ produced, making it non-environmentally friendly.⁷ Moreover, H₂ requires high storage pressure

and its wide flammability range (4-75%) poses significant safety risks, as leakages can lead to explosions. On-site H₂ generation addresses these challenges by producing H₂ directly at the point of use, supplying it instantly where needed, and eliminating the need for storage and transport, and the associated energy conversion loss.⁸

Figure 1 (A) Global primary energy sources and (B) Global H₂ demand. Non-renewables account for 76.7% of total energy.⁹ H₂ demand is projected to increase sixfold in 50 years.¹⁰

Globally, 7 million tonnes of aluminium (Al) waste end up in landfills yearly.¹¹ Using this waste for H₂ production could recover value through upcycling while reducing the environmental impacts of disposal. Normally, a thin oxide layer prevents water from reacting with Al, inhibiting H₂ production. A gallium (Ga) catalyst, which is liquid near room temperature, disrupts this oxide layer to enable H₂ production. As a regenerative catalyst, Ga can be fully recovered and reused, lowering costs.¹² Different Ga percentages in the alloy affect H₂ yields. In 1967, Woodall found that a 5 wt% Al-Ga alloy could yield H₂ when mixed with water.¹³ As interest in H₂ fuel grew, he developed a 28 wt% Al solid alloy in 2007.¹⁴ A recent study identified 77.8 wt% Ga as the theoretical optimum, offering the highest adsorption energies for oxygen and water.¹⁵ Therefore, optimising the Ga ratio is important to prevent passivation without incurring excessive costs.

Figure 2 Ball-and-stick models of caffeine and citric acid, and electrical double layer formation around a Ga droplet.^{16,17} In ionic solutions, Ga develops a net negative surface charge; ions bind to Ga surfaces at the Stern layer and form a mobile ionic cloud in the diffuse layer.

Every day, 2 billion cups of coffee and 5 billion cups of tea are consumed worldwide, producing approximately 15 billion kg of waste yearly.^{18,19} Similarly, 120 billion kg of citrus fruits are discarded annually due to spoilage, pests, and handling damage.²⁰ Caffeine (C₈H₁₀N₄O₂) and citric acid (C₆H₈O₇) act as effective chelating agents that increase H₂ yield by binding aluminium ions. In 3.0 M sodium chloride (NaCl), 0.001 M caffeine achieves 99% H₂ yield within 15 minutes with a higher eGaIn

recovery. Seawater also increases H_2 yield by corroding Al_2O_3 through Cl^- ions and increasing H^+ availability from water dissociation.^{21,22} Simultaneously, ionic medium of sea water further disrupts the aluminium oxide layer and increases available reaction sites. In a 1 wt% NaCl solution with 1 wt% citric acid at 30°C, reactivity increases by 280% compared to citric acid alone.²³ When combined with the Ga catalyst, this further enhances the reaction to maximise H_2 yield. Hypotheses of the experiment are as follows:

- H1. As Ga percentage in Al-Ga alloy increases, H_2 yield, Ga recovery and reaction rate increase.
- H2. As reaction temperature increases, H_2 yield, Ga recovery and reaction rate increases.
- H3. As chelators concentration increases, H_2 yield increases, Ga recovery decreases.
- H4. As NaCl concentration increases, H_2 yield and reaction rate increase, Ga recovery decreases.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Methodology

The Ga content in Al-Ga alloys is changed from 0 wt% to 100 wt%, with 0.25 g Al foil reacting in 50 mL deionised water at 40°C for 10 minutes, after which H_2 volume was measured. After each trial, the flask contents were decanted, Ga was collected using a separatory funnel, washed with deionised water, and weight. Residues combined from all trials were further tested using centrifugation, filtration, and evaporation to dryness for a second round of Ga recovery. Recycled Al waste was also tested under the same conditions. Citric acid concentrations from 0.05 M to 0.1M, fruit and organic additives including oranges, lemons, tomatoes, spent coffee grounds (SCG), and spent tea leaves (STL) at concentration of 0.1 wt% to 5 wt%, NaCl concentrations from 0 M to 2.5 M were each tested independently. Finally, optimal conditions identified from each variable were combined and tested with seawater.

Figure 3 Experimental setup diagram. (A) H_2 gas is collected and measured through water displacement in a measuring cylinder; fused $CaCl_2$ removes water vapour. (B) The densest liquid Ga is collected from the bottom of separatory funnel.

Figure 4 Experimental setup (A), Main Ga recovery (B), and Further Ga recovery methods (C–E). (A) Aluminium–water reaction (AWR) in a coffee and NaCl solution. (B–E) Red circles mark Ga: (B) Ga settles at the bottom of a separatory funnel; (C) mixture centrifuged at 10,000 RPM for 10 minutes; (D) mixture heated in an oven at 90°C until water evaporates; (E) mixture filtered through filter paper to collect Ga.

2.2 Mathematical formula

Graphs were created using Matplotlib, Pandas, SciPy, and NumPy in Python to visualise trends and patterns and to verify the hypotheses. Figures 4A, 4B, and 5A use a logistic function: $f(x) = \frac{A}{1 + e^{-B(x-C)}}$ with the lag phase, rapid growth, and a plateau as the reaction approaches equilibrium; A denotes the asymptotic maximum, B the rate constant (curve steepness), and C the inflection point. Polynomials up to the third degree are added for fitting. Figures 6A, 7A, and 7B use an exponential decay function: $f(x) = Ae^{-Bx} + C$ to characterise decreases in H₂ yield and Ga recovery at higher NaCl or chelator concentrations; A is the initial value at $x = 0$, B the decay constant, and C the asymptote as concentration $\rightarrow \infty$. Figures 5B, 6B, 8A and 8B use a logarithmic polynomial function to model H₂ increase over time: $f(t) = A \cdot \log(t)^2 + B \cdot \log(t) + C$, showing a steep initial increase followed by a gradual plateau, with polynomials added for fitting. A controls the curvature, determining how sharply the curve rises as t increases; B controls the slope; C is the y-intercept.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Reaction trends and key parameters

The observations confirm H1. The optimal Ga content is 80 wt%, achieving 53.53% H₂ yield and 80.70% Ga recovery. While 90 wt% and 95 wt% Ga had slightly higher recovery, the increase in H₂ yield was minimal (Figure 5A). This matches the theoretical optimum of 77.78% H₂ yield calculated through DFT.¹⁵ While other studies tested AWR in alkaline solutions and modelled exponential yield increases using the Arrhenius equation, a logarithmic trend was observed here due to the dependence of Al–Ga on active reaction sites.^{11,24} As shown in Figure 5B, H₂ yield and Ga recovery increase with temperature, reaching a maximum H₂ yield of 70.13% yield at 90°C. Higher temperatures increase molecular kinetic energy and collision frequency, thereby increasing H₂ yield and confirming H2; however, if passivation recurs, the effect is minimal. As shown in Figure 6A, increasing citric acid concentration enhances both H₂ yield and Ga recovery, peaking at 87.26% yield and 97.20% recovery at 0.10 M citric acid. Among juices used as chelators, lemon achieves the highest H₂ yield at 78.69%,

with a *Ga* recovery of 97.10% (Figure 6B), likely due to its high citric acid content. These trends can be explained by the chelation mechanism: Chelators bond to insoluble $Al(OH)_3$, preventing active sites blockage and sustaining AWR, thereby increasing H_2 yield. However, at high concentrations, chelators may also bind to Ga^{3+} , reducing *Ga* coalescence and recovery. As a result H_2 yield and *Ga* recovery exhibit opposing trends with increasing chelator concentration, confirming H3.

Figure 5 Effect of Ga content (A) and temperature (B) on H_2 yield and *Ga* recovery.

Figure 6 Effect of citric acid concentration on H_2 yield and *Ga* recovery (A), and chelator types on H_2 yield (B).

Figure 7 Effect of NaCl concentration on H_2 yield and *Ga* recovery (A), and Chelator types on H_2 yield (B).

As illustrated in Figure 7A, H_2 yield and *Ga* recovery decrease as NaCl concentration increases, with a maximum H_2 yield of 89.93% and *Ga* recovery of 98.00% at 0.05 M NaCl. In NaCl, the Stern layer of the electrical double layer (EDL) adsorbs Na^+ and Cl^- ions, while the diffuse layer balances the charge, slowing water access but improving *Ga* recovery by maintaining cohesive and recoverable droplets. At low ion concentrations in the EDL, a weak electric field near the Al surface causes anodic polarisation ($\Delta\phi > 0$), shifting the surface potential to positive. This promotes electron removal,

causing Al to oxidise more readily and accelerating AWR.²⁸ Contrastingly, the EDL becomes densely packed with cations at high ion concentrations, generating a strong electric field and inducing cathodic polarisation ($\Delta\phi < 0$).²⁸ This shifts the surface potential to negative, reducing Al's tendency to lose electrons and inhibiting anodic reactions. Among fruit juices tested, lemon achieved an H₂ yield of 91.54% in 0.05 M NaCl, surpassing the 89.93% yield of 0.025 M citric acid (Figure B), its theoretical equivalent. Additional chelators like malic and ascorbic acids may increase chelation efficiency.

Figure 8 Effect of SCG and STL concentration (A) and NaCl concentration (B) on H₂ yield and Ga recovery.

As shown in Figure 8A, H₂ yield increases with SCG and STL concentration while Ga recovery decreases. At 0.05 M NaCl, SCG achieved an H₂ yield of 86.72% and Ga recovery of 96.10%, while STL achieved an H₂ yield of 85.12% and Ga recovery of 97.40%. In deionised water, SCG achieved an H₂ yield of 88.33% and Ga recovery of 90.30%, while STL achieved an H₂ yield of 86.72% and Ga recovery of 92.20%. With 1% SCG or STL, higher NaCl concentrations further reduce both H₂ yield and Ga recovery (Figure 8B). These differences can be attributed to the distinct chelation mechanisms of each additive. Citric acid chelates Al³⁺ ions through its three carboxyl groups and one hydroxyl group, with its carboxylic acid groups readily losing protons to form carboxylate anions that act as electron donors and form strong multidentate bonds with metal ions, yielding more H₂ than SCG and STL.²⁵ In contrast, caffeine's nitrogen atoms form coordinate bonds with Al, creating a chelate complex. As SCG contains water-soluble caffeine that forms weaker nitrogen coordinate bonds with Al, it produces slightly more H₂ but recovers less Ga than STL.^{26,27} Overall, low NaCl concentrations combined with citric acid, SCG, or STL improve H₂ yield, Ga recovery, and reaction rate, partially confirming H4. Diluted seawater slightly reduces H₂ yield compared to 0.05 M NaCl due to an increased EDL effect from the higher ion concentration.

Figure 9 H₂ Yield from Different chelators in seawater (A) and Al waste sources (B).

Among chelators tested in seawater, lemon proved to be the most effective, achieving an H_2 yield of 93.15%, outperforming both SCG and STL (Figure 9A). As shown in Figure 9B, tests conducted at 35°C revealed that Al trays and cans produced higher H_2 yields of 5.89 and 4.28 percentage points above pure Al foil, respectively, while wires and powder produced lower yields of 13.38 and 19.80 percentage points below. The superior performance of Al trays and cans relative to pure Al foil can be attributed to their alloy composition. Trays and cans are commonly alloyed with Si and Mg; Si creates smaller grains with more active sites, enhancing Ga penetration and oxide layer disruption.²⁹ whereas Mg, being, corrosion-resistant, reduces H_2 yield and forms Mg_2Si with Si, creating barriers that further lower yields.³⁰ In contrast, wires and powders, despite having higher surface area-to-volume ratios, possess thicker oxide layers that require greater Ga content to maintain H_2 yields. As shown in Figure 10, centrifugation obtains the highest Ga recovery at 99.91%, compared to filtration and evaporation to dryness; however, its high equipment and energy costs make it less practical for scaling up. Filtration, achieving 99.59% Ga recovery, is more viable, particularly with reusable filters and repeated recovery rounds to further improve recovery. Evaporation to dryness is the least effective method, with a total Ga recovery of 99.17%.

Figure 10 Effect of Ga recovery methods on Total Ga recovery.

3.2 Limitations and Recommendations

Ga forms covalent Ga–Ga dimers in its solid state, creating strong directional forces within the lattice, causing high surface cohesion. When melted, these bonds break, allowing Ga to flow as a liquid.³¹ Maintaining reaction temperatures above 30°C prevents solidification and improves recovery rates. Collected H_2 may be impure due to the non-vacuum setup; a gas-tight collection system would provide a more accurate measurement. A vacuum system with $CaCl_2$ drying would allow purer H_2 collection and is more suitable for larger-scale applications. While high temperatures (90°C) improve reaction rates, the energy required for heating may exceed the energy gained from H_2 production. The exothermic nature of AWR increases reaction flask temperatures; scaling up could utilise thermally insulated reaction flasks to retain heat, reducing water consumption and maintaining continuous AWR to sustain higher temperatures and improve reaction rates. As pure caffeine was unavailable, SCG and STL were used as substitutes. Future studies should compare pure caffeine with SCG and STL to determine whether other compounds in these materials affect AWR.

3.3 Contributions and Practical Applications

This research advances low-emission H_2 production, green energy, and waste upcycling. Al is a high-density H_2 storage medium, greater than compressed H_2 gas and metal hydrides. Testing AWR

with Ga across wide temperature ranges and using fruits, SCG, STL, and seawater demonstrates its adaptability across diverse environments while upcycling waste. By reducing reliance on fossil fuels and mitigating carbon emissions, this system aligns with UNSDG 7 (affordable, sustainable energy) and UNSDG 12 (responsible consumption and production).³² Additionally, this system also holds significant potential across multiple sectors. In transport, on-site H₂ generation could reduce range anxiety on H₂ powered vehicles, which already operating on roads today.³³ Airports are also exploring H₂ as an aviation fuel³⁴, and Singapore has launched the world's first ship using seawater for H₂ production,³⁵ with plans to open its first H₂ power plant by 2029.³⁶ In defence, this system could support submarines, where fuel cells are already employed for silent operation to avoiding sonar detection.^{37,38} Beyond transport, Al-Ga H₂ production offers an energy solution for remote and off-grid locations, relying on locally sourced Al waste and minimal equipment. Scaling this system aligns with global net-zero and the \$11.7 trillion transport market.³⁹ With further development, the system could even support space exploration through alkaline fuel cells, as used on Apollo missions since the 1960s, utilising water source in space, including those from ancient Martian oceans.^{40,41} Mars' crust contains 5.6% Al, and NASA recognises H₂ as a key exploration fuel.^{42,43} Moreover, H₂ can also has industrial applications in chemical production, as a reducing agent, and in metallurgy.⁴⁴

4. CONCLUSION

This study optimises low-cost on-site hydrogen generation via the AWR using Ga oxide disruption in saline medium, incorporating food waste sources including STL, SCG, tomatoes, lemons and oranges. An 80% Ga alloy with 0.05 mol NaCl and 1% SCG had an 88.33% H₂ yield and 90.30% Ga recovery. The findings indicate that small amounts of chelators and NaCl increase H₂ yield and Ga recovery. Future research should focus to quantify and identify post-reaction residues. While Al(OH)₃ is known to form during AWR, X-ray diffraction (XRD) can identify other compounds that may form with fruits, SCG, and STL to see determine their impact on Ga recovery. Additionally, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) can be used to study the surface morphology of Al-Ga alloy before and after the reaction to understand how its structure and active sites affect H₂ production and Ga recovery. This analysis can explain how chelators affect the alloys and advance research toward developing catalysts with higher hydrogen yields. Finally, studying the time required for Ga to alloy with Al could improve homogeneity, oxide disruption, and overall H₂ yield.

5. AUTHOR INFORMATION

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Author Contributions

F.C.G and L.J. conducted the experiments, conception, design, data analysis, and drafting of the manuscript.

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